

DECODE – Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement – a daunting task?

How does the DECODE project embed PPIE in everything we do?

We have four groups of people with learning disabilities (LD), family and paid carers of people with LD, who our PPIE leads meet with monthly. They have additionally joined us on research presentations to contribute to panels, spoken in videos and radio broadcasts and worked with us on research outputs. These wonderful people have helped us develop our understanding and ability to communicate with the learning disability (LD) community and guided us on what issues affect them, to enable us to talk to health and social care professional participants. It is however with some trepidation that we (or rather I) have reached out beyond the comfort of our local LD community to engage a wider audience.

How does the DECODE project recruit PPIE members?

These named or potential stakeholders are sometimes personal contacts and sometimes aspired connections, some distant, some new or people/bodies we've come across through the project, but most are less closely connected with DECODE as a project. Our wider network is more of an unknown quantity, national and international figures and bodies that have a close tie, but they may not even know it yet!

How does the DECODE project translate clusters and trajectories into actionable insights through stakeholder engagement?

DECODE project's 4th and final work package is focused on developing actionable insights for effective care coordination for people with LD which follows months of data analysis and information gathering across WP1-3 and development of understanding of actionable insights. As part of this, Spring 2024, was the start of WP4 workshops with stakeholder groups. These groups include; people with learning disabilities, family and paid carers and health and social care professionals and additionally; health and social care commissioners, charities, policy makers and technologists. The latter four of these was a slightly more daunting task but thankfully AIM RSF had the right session at the right time with a timely 'AIM Stakeholder Engagement Training' 30 April, organised by Mon and Team.

How did AIM RSF help us to engage stakeholders?

The session, led by Jo Clift, who worked in the UK Government for 20 years and has a wealth of policy engagement knowledge and connections, immediately made me feel less daunted and told me to ignore the imposter syndrome in my head and tackle the task in-hand. We have common interests to explore with our national and international 'connections' and whilst a named introduction might be the most effective way of getting a response, gentle persistence and a multi-pronged approach can work in gaining attention and interest of our more remote people of interest.

Our takeaway messages?

Whilst we may be at the bottom of the engagement pyramid, of giving and receiving information, it is only through these interactions that we start to build bridges and potentially start to develop relations and maybe, one-day, start to influence them. Jo taught me to be bold, to reach out and not be thwarted by potential early rejection. So, with this in mind, we reached out to invite along the good and influential to participate in a workshop, to ask for their input to how we use our research findings and outcomes to best effect. Some ignored us, some are attending and maybe through them we'll make further connections. The first workshop went very well, so I'm hopeful

others will follow in the same vein. Jo said quality of relationships matter, know your audience and what you have to offer so our workshops have taken this on board.

Someone recently said, aren't you putting the cart before the horse, by reaching out to your stakeholders when you research outcomes are only beginning to emerge. Jo has taught me that it's only through engaging now, whether through recognition of our project or early chats with our team members, that we'll take stakeholders with us. We're immensely proud of what we're doing and want to make a difference, alongside every other fellow AIM project. Thanks to Jo for giving us a framework to develop our pathways and imparting some confidence to believe we can have impact.